

Adaptive Mechanism of Restoring the Tone of Masticatory Muscles in Non-Removable Prosthetics Supported by Dental Implants

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Abstract: This clinical study presents an analysis of the adaptation of 40 patients to non-removable dental prostheses supported by endosteal implants, compared with those supported by natural teeth. The study of masticatory function was carried out before treatment, and then at 3-6 and 6-12 months following the placement of non-removable prostheses supported by endosteal implants. The dominant chewing side was determined, along with the masticatory pressure force using gnathodynamometry, the average maximum amplitude, and muscle force using surface interference electromyography. Measurements were taken separately on the functional dominant and non-dominant sides. In the comparison group, similar parameters were studied in 25 individuals (10 men and 15 women aged 36-60 years) with partial tooth loss, who required dental orthopedic treatment on one jaw and had metal-ceramic fixed bridge prostheses placed on natural teeth. The results of treatment were evaluated based on an objective test using a physician's questionnaire "Adaptation Forecast to Prosthetic Structures" and the calculation of the disadaptation coefficient in points. Based on the presence (15 cases, 60%) or absence (25 cases, 40%) of a change in the dominant chewing side after treatment, patients were divided into two subgroups. It was found that a change in the functional dominant side is associated with relatively unstable masticatory function indicators, which coincides with increased loads on the prostheses during the 3-6 month adaptation period. This should be considered when planning an individual adaptation program for patients to dental orthopedic structures.

Keywords: dental implantation, gnathodynamometry, electromyography, physician questionnaire, muscle adaptation, disadaptation.

Summary: The clinical study provides an analysis of the adaptation of 40 patients to fixed dentures supported by intraosseous implants and supported by natural teeth. The study of chewing function was carried out before the start of treatment, as well as 3-6 and 6-12 months after the installation of fixed dentures supported by intraosseous implants. The predominant (functionally dominant) side of chewing, the strength of chewing pressure using gnathodynamometry, the average maximum amplitude and the magnitude of muscle force using surface interference electromyography were determined. Measurements were carried out separately on the functionally dominant and non-dominant sides. In the comparison group, the same indicators were studied in 25 people (10 men and 15 women aged 36-60 years), with partial absence of teeth requiring dental orthopedic treatment on

one of the jaws with the manufacture of fixed dentures, and patients were fitted with a metal-ceramic bridge based on natural teeth. The treatment results were assessed on the basis of an objective test using the medical questionnaire "Forecast of adaptation to orthopedic structures" with the calculation of the disadaptation coefficient in points. Due to the presence (15 cases, 60%) or absence (25 cases, 40%) of a change in the dominant side of chewing after completion of treatment, patients were divided into two subgroups. It has been established that a change in the functionally dominant side is accompanied by relatively unstable indicators of chewing function, which is combined during 3-6 months of adaptation with increased loads on the installed dentures, which must be taken into account when planning an individual complex of patient adaptation to dental orthopedic structures.

Relevance of the Problem:

Restoring included defects in dental arches by placing non-removable prosthetic constructions supported by endosteal (dental) implants is considered to be the "gold standard" in modern orthopedic dentistry. Positive results of such prosthetics have been summarized in a number of large retrospective studies, and the effectiveness mentioned in these studies (approximately 95-96%) has been assessed based only on the preservation of osteointegration, the integrity of the installed structure, and quality of life questionnaires [1, 2]. The restoration of masticatory surfaces, by definition, is accompanied by a reorganization of the masticatory segment of the dentoalveolar system. Therefore, some specialists rightly consider the study of these functional indicators an essential part of monitoring patient adaptation to non-removable dental prostheses [3, 4]. When restoring lost teeth with prostheses supported by endosteal implants, a functional segment of the masticatory apparatus is created, with new loads transmitted directly into the bone tissue, bypassing the reflex zones of the periodontal ligament [5].

When studying the functional state of the muscles of the maxillofacial region, electromyographic and electromyotometric methods are used. From a functional perspective, the muscles of the dentoalveolar system are conventionally divided into perioral and intra-oral muscles. Orthopedically, the muscles are considered as three functional circles: the mimetic muscles, the masticatory muscles, and the tongue muscles. Studying the masticatory and mimetic musculature in normal conditions and in cases of anomalies in the development of the dentoalveolar system is of great importance: it helps to identify individual features of muscle function caused by occlusal anomalies. An analysis is conducted of the changes that occur in the function of muscles or their nervous apparatus in all cases of treating anomalies of the dentoalveolar system [6].

Electromyography is the recording of muscle bio-potentials to study their physiological activity. Electromyographic studies can be used to determine dysfunctions of the masticatory and mimetic muscles at rest, during muscle contraction, and during movement of the lower jaw, typical for various bite anomalies. A multi-channel electromyograph "Diza" can be used for this purpose. Electromyograms are recorded on perforated photographic film at a rotation speed of 5 mm/s or on an oscilloscope photographic paper 10 cm wide at a speed of 20 mm/s (Fig. 1).

Photo. 1. Graphical recording of the masticatory muscle strength using an apparatus with two levers and rubber diaphragms inside (1), the function of the left temporalis muscle using a cylinder with a rubber diaphragm inside (2), and the function of the right temporalis muscle with a rubber balloon and button (3).

Relevance of the Problem. The restoration of partial edentulism using fixed dental prostheses supported by intraosseous (dental) implants is regarded as the "gold standard" in modern prosthodontics. Positive outcomes of such prosthetic treatment have been summarized in several large retrospective studies; the effectiveness indicated in these studies (about 95-96%) has been evaluated primarily by the criteria of osteointegration maintenance, the integrity of the established prosthesis, and quality of life questionnaires [1, 2]. The restoration of masticatory surfaces is, by definition, accompanied by remodeling of the masticatory apparatus of the dentofacial system. In this regard, many specialists rightly consider the study of these functional indicators to be an essential part of monitoring the adaptation of patients to fixed dental prostheses [3, 4]. When restoring lost teeth with prostheses supported by intraosseous implants, a functioning segment of the masticatory apparatus is formed, introducing new loads directly to the bone tissue, bypassing the reflex zones of the periodontal ligament [5].

When studying the functional state of the muscles of the craniofacial region, electromyographic and electromyotometric methods are used. Functionally, the muscles of the dentofacial system are conventionally divided into perioral and intraoral muscles. From an orthopedic perspective, these muscles can be classified into three functional groups: facial muscles, masticatory muscles, and tongue muscles. The study of masticatory and facial muscles, both in normal conditions and in the case of malocclusions, is of great importance, as it helps identify individual functional features of the muscles caused by occlusal anomalies. Analyzing the changes that occur in muscle function or their nerve apparatus is crucial in the treatment of dentofacial anomalies [6].

Electromyography is the recording of the bio-potentials of muscles to study their physiological activity. Electromyographic studies can identify dysfunctions of the masticatory and facial muscles at rest, during tension, and with movements of the lower jaw, which are characteristic of various occlusal anomalies. A multi-channel electromyograph, such as the "Diza" model, can be used for this purpose. Electromyograms are recorded on perforated photographic film at a speed of 5 mm/s or on oscilloscope

photographic paper 10 cm wide with a recording speed of 20 mm/s (Fig. 1). Graphical registration of the strength of masticatory muscles using an apparatus with two levers and rubber diaphragms inside (1), function of the left temporalis muscle with a cylinder containing a rubber diaphragm (2), and function of the right temporalis muscle with a rubber balloon and button (3).

Surface or needle electrodes are used to study muscle condition. Surface electrodes are placed at the center of muscle contraction. To ensure consistency in electromyographic studies, electrodes are placed with equal distances between them. For this purpose, electrodes are positioned in special devices made from elastic plastics or other materials. They are applied to the same areas of the skin, ensuring identical recordings of bioelectric signals during repeated studies throughout the course of treatment and when assessing the long-term results. After palpating the muscle contraction center, a motor point is marked on the skin of the face. A goniometer is applied to the corner of the lower jaw, and the marked point on the face is measured in both horizontal and vertical directions according to the scale of the goniometer. These coordinates are then recorded on the examination chart.

For the study of temporalis muscles, electrodes are placed on the anterior, middle, or posterior parts of the muscle on both sides. For the study of the orbicularis oris muscle, electrodes are placed on the middle parts of the upper and lower lips, and for the study of the mentalis muscle, electrodes are placed on the chin area. Before placing the electrodes, the corresponding areas of the skin are thoroughly cleaned with alcohol and a special paste is applied. It is preferable to register the activity of paired muscles in a relaxed state, under tension (including when the teeth are clenched), and under various loads on the lower jaw. Of particular interest is the study of the electrical activity of these muscles during chewing, involuntary swallowing, and forced swallowing. To determine the degree of participation of the orbicularis oris, mentalis, masticatory, and other muscles in these actions, electromyographic recordings from multiple channels are required simultaneously.

In cases of orthognathic occlusion, electromyography of the masticatory muscles recorded at rest typically shows low-voltage oscillations, reflecting weak electrical activity. This type of recording appears as almost a straight line [13].

The results of these load effects are undoubtedly involved in evaluating categories such as patient satisfaction with the treatment outcome, the prognosis for the longevity of the installed prosthetic devices, and the prognosis for late complications of implantation. However, all of these aspects have not been sufficiently studied up to now.

Aim of the Study– to study the dynamics of adaptation of masticatory muscles to fixed dental prostheses supported by intraosseous implants.

Materials and Methods. The clinical group, based on informed consent, consisted of 15 patients (5 men and 10 women) aged 36 to 60 years with partial tooth loss, requiring prosthodontic treatment on one of the jaws with fixed prostheses supported by intraosseous implants. Exclusion criteria from the group included somatic diseases significantly affecting bone tissue regeneration, autoimmune and oncological diseases, and mental disorders. Pregnant and breastfeeding women were also excluded from the study.

The study of masticatory function was conducted before the treatment, as well as 3-6 months and 6-12 months after the installation of fixed prostheses supported by intraosseous implants. Before treatment began, functional tests were used to determine the predominant (functionally dominant) side of chewing, which, as expected, was the right side in about a 2:1 ratio, with rare cases of mixed type where it was impossible to determine the dominant side [6]. The strength of masticatory pressure was assessed using gnathodynamometry and electromyography.

In the comparison group, the same indicators were studied in 25 people (10 men and 15 women) aged 36 to 60 years, with partial tooth loss, requiring prosthodontic treatment on one jaw and the installation of a metal-ceramic bridge prosthesis based on natural teeth. The age and gender distribution in both the clinical group and the comparison group were similar (Table 1).

age	Clinical Group			Comparison Group		
	all	male	female	all	male	female
36-40 age	5	1	2	7	2	4
41-45 age	4	1	3	4	2	2
46-50 age	3	1	3	6	3	6
51-60 age	3	2	2	8	3	3

In the clinical group, after the placement of fixed prostheses supported by intraosseous implants, 15 (37.5%) patients experienced a change in the dominant side of chewing within 3-6 months, which we interpreted as a return to the status existing before the formation of the included defects. These patients were classified into the first clinical subgroup, while patients with unchanged chewing side dominance (usually the right side) during and after treatment were classified into the second clinical subgroup.

The chewing pressure force on the functional dominant and non-dominant sides in the clinical subgroups before treatment, as well as in the comparison group, showed similar values. After 3-6 months of treatment, in the first clinical subgroup, the value of this indicator increased by 12.4% on the dominant side and by 14.8% on the non-dominant side of chewing. This change was minimal in the second clinical subgroup, where the values of this indicator remained similar to those measured before treatment (see Table 2).

Table 2

Functional indicators of the masticatory link of the dental system in patients of the clinical group and the comparison group (M + m)

Side	Comparison group (n = 36)	Clinical group		
		Deadlines	First subgroup (n=41)	Second subgroup (n=23)
Masticatory muscle pressure force, N				
Dominant	233.0±8.9	Before treatment	227.3±8.4	225.3 ± 11.4
		3-6 months	262.3 ± 12.0 *#	236.7 ± 13.3
		7-12 months	255.7 ± 10.2*#	230.5 ± 10.8
Non-dominant	196.7 ± 7.7	Before treatment	190.8 ± 7.7	197.8 ± 12.5
		3-6 months	225.2±10.2#	207.6 ± 13.6
		7-12 months	213.6±9.6	201.3 ±11.9
EMG amplitude, mV				
Dominant	1.42 ± 0.08	Before treatment	1.27 ± 0.12	1.34±0.14
		3-6 months	1.67 ± 0.12 *	1.36 ± 0.09
		7-12 months	1.52 ± 0.13 *	1.49 ± 0.13
Non-dominant	1.19 ± 0.07	Before treatment	0.89 ± 0.10 *	1.10 ± 0.09
		3-6 months	1.43 ± 0.10 *	1.18±0.11
		7-12 months	1.31 ± 0.09 *#	1.25±0.08
Contraction force, μV-s				
Dominant	151.4 ± 6.4	Before treatment	165.0±12.9	143.0±8.7
		3-6 months	236.6 ± 14.8 *#	166.3 ± 9.9
		7-12 months	198.5 ± 12.6 *#	165.4 ± 11.9
Non-dominant	98.6 ± 5.1	Before treatment	122.6 ± 11.8	99.4 ± 6.9
		3-6 months	175.1 ± 13.7 *#	116.0 ± 12.3
		7-12 months	140.8 ± 10.4*	102.6±9.3

* - reliable differences with the values in the comparison group,
- reliable differences with pre-treatment values in the same subgroup

Before Treatment:

Before the start of treatment, patients in the clinical group exhibited moderate decreases in the EMG values, with a more noticeable reduction on the non-dominant side in the first clinical subgroup (33.7% lower than in the comparison group). In the second clinical subgroup, the decrease in EMG values did not exceed 7.6%.

After Treatment:

After the completion of treatment, within 3-6 months, normalization of the EMG amplitude and the average contraction force was observed in the second clinical subgroup, with improvements occurring approximately equally on both sides of chewing. In contrast, in the first clinical subgroup, there was an increase in the values of the analyzed parameters, particularly on the dominant side of chewing (by more than one-third). This was interpreted as reflecting the remodeling of the masticatory muscles during the process of changing the dominant side of chewing.

The data show that the process of returning to the habitual dominant side of chewing after the placement of fixed prostheses supported by intraosseous implants is accompanied by a relative deterioration in the overall treatment outcomes, as assessed by the objective evaluation scale (KDA). In the first clinical subgroup, during the adaptation period to the prostheses (3-6 months after prosthesis placement), the scores decreased by 37.0%, whereas in the second clinical subgroup, the reduction was only 22.3%.

parameter	comparison group (n = 36)	Clinical group		
		time periods	First group	Second group
KDA	-	Before treatment	-	-
		3-6 mec.	11,5 ± 0,4	5,2 ± 0,3
		7-12 mec.	6,7 ± 0,3	4,4 ± 0,3

Analysis of the results: The analysis was based on well-established concepts that the indicators obtained from instrumental methods for studying the masticatory system of the dentofacial complex reliably reflect its functional efficiency and complement each other when used together [9, 10]. The study showed that in nearly two-thirds of patients, during the 3-6 month adaptation period to non-removable prostheses supported by endosteal implants, a return to the habitual functionally dominant side of chewing occurs. This process, as indicated by the results, is accompanied by a temporary decrease in satisfaction with the treatment outcomes from both the physician's and the patient's perspective. This is partly due to the period of relatively high and unfamiliar loads on the installed prostheses, caused by increased functional activity of the masticatory muscles. Uncontrolled loads on the prostheses supported by endosteal implants can lead to microtraumas, infection penetration into the osteointegration zone, and disruption of the integration process due to secondary complications, potentially leading to implant loss [11][12].

Conclusion: The period from 3-6 months following the installation of non-removable prostheses supported by endosteal implants is characterized by frequent changes in the dominant chewing side, relatively unstable indicators of masticatory function, and increased load on the masticatory muscles and installed dental prostheses. For these

patients, relatively low indicators are observed according to functional methods, including electromyography and the objective physician's questionnaire with the calculation of the Disadaptation Coefficient (DAC). These factors should be taken into account when planning an individualized adaptation program for patients with dental orthopedic constructions.

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